

THE MATHEMATICAL SOLUTION FOR THE BEAL CONJECTURE

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Abstract-

*The Beal conjecture is an unsolved number problem. It was formulated in 1993 by Andrew Beal ,A Banker and an amature mathematician during investigating generalization of **Fermats** Last Theorem [1] [2] since 1997. He offered a monetary prize for an impressive proof of this conjecture . At present no suitable proof has been produced . In this article I also provided the clear and a systematic proof of this conjecture .*

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1.Introduction

IN 1993 , Andrew Beal , a Texas Banker and a number theory Mathematician formulated a number theory which he named “Beal conjecture” . After 4 years in In 1997 he publicly announced to offer a \$ 5,000 prize money for the peer review proof. By now he increased the prize money to a sum of \$ 1,000,000 . Many number of experts , mathematicians and scholars have published their research articles on the proof of this number problem but they could not present a suitable proof . I am also presenting a proof in this article .

2.The Beal conjecture

Let A,B,C,X,Y,Z be positive integers , with X,Y,Z greater than 2. The Beal conjecture states that

If :

$$A^X + B^Y = C^Z \quad (1)$$

Then A,B,C must have a common prime factor and all variables should have distinct value.

3. Conventions

Author has used symbols and conventions to proof the conjecture where O_a , O_b and O_c are odd symbols . And E_a , E_b and E_c are even symbols . where as 1,3,5,7..... represent odd no. and 2,4,6,8..... represent even numbers .

4. Conditions of addition operations

I observed three different conditions for solving conjecture

Condition 1:

$$O_a + O_b = E_c$$

Condition 2:

$$O_a + E_b = O_c$$

Condition 3 :

$$E_a + E_b = E_c$$

5.Verification

Here author has solved the equation very clearly , and found out a common prime factor in the equations as well as represented distinct exponents according to original definition of Beal conjecture which can be seen in the numerical examples . Hence Beal conjecture is quite true .

6.The proof

Below is given the proof for the Beal conjecture using the three conditions .

6.1 Condition 1

$$O_a + O_b = E_c$$

Let ' O_a ' Represent A

Let ' O_b ' Represent B

Let ' E_c ' Represent C

$$A + B = C \quad (2)$$

Let $A = 1$, Let $B \neq 1$ and Let $C \neq 1$ where $B = B_1^y$ and $y=1$

Let $C = C_1^z$ and $z \geq 3$

Equation 2 is an ordinary addition operation and variables are represented in exponential forms .

$$1 + B_1^y = C_1^z \quad (3)$$

According to author's observation equation is multiplied 3 times by B_1^z

$$1 \times B_1^z \times B_1^z \times B_1^z + B_1^y \times B_1^z \times B_1^z \times B_1^z = C_1^z \times B_1^z \times B_1^z \times B_1^z \quad (4)$$

By applying the laws of indices I can have

$$(B_1)^{z+z+z} + (B_1)^{y+z+z} = (C_1 \times B_1)^{z+z+z}$$

$$(B_1)^{3z} + (B_1)^{y+3z} = (C_1 \times B_1)^{4z} \quad (5)$$

Now after adjusting the exponents of equation 5 it can be formed Beal equation .

According to author's observation B_1 is a common prime factor in above equation.

Comment – condition 1 clearly proof the Beal equations .

6.1.1 Numerical examples

1. Derivation of Beal conjecture from the equation

$$1 + 7 = 8$$

Solution –

$$1 + 7 = 8$$

$$1+7^1=2^3$$

Multiplying through by 7^3 3 times

$$1 \times 7^3 \times 7^3 \times 7^3 + 7^1 \times 7^3 \times 7^3 \times 7^3 = 2^3 \times 7^3 \times 7^3 \times 7^3$$

Applying the rules of indices

$$7^9+7^{10}=(7\times 7\times 7\times 2)^3$$

Adjusting the exponents of equation it can be proved Beal conjecture

$$7^9+(49)^5=(686)^3$$

Now 7 is common prime factor in the above equation.

Beal conjecture is true for condition 1

2. Derivation of Beal equation from example

$$1+127 = 128$$

Solution

$$1+127=128$$

$$1+127^1=2^7$$

Multiplying the equation three times by 127^7

$$1\times 127^7\times 127^7\times 127^7+127^1\times 127^7\times 127^7\times 127^7=2^7\times 127^7\times 127^7\times 127^7$$

Applying the rules of indices

$$(127)^{21}+(127)^{22}=(2\times 127\times 127\times 127)^7$$

$$127^{21}+(16129)^{11}=(4096766)^7$$

127 is a common prime factor of above equation.

6.2 Condition 2

$$O_a+E_b=O_c$$

Let 'O_a' represent A

Let 'E_b' represent B

Let 'O_c' represent C

$$A+B=C \quad (6)$$

Let $A = 1$, Let $B \neq 1$, and Let $C \neq 1$

Equation 6 is an ordinary addition operation and A ,B and C are an exponential format.

Let $B = B_1^y$, where $y \geq 3$

Let $C = C_1^z$ where $z = 1$

$$1+B_1^y = C_1^z \quad (7)$$

C_1^y multiplies the equation two times .

So Beal conjecture can be made .

$$1 \times C_1^{y \times C_1^y} + B_1^{y \times C_1^y \times C_1^y} = C_1^{z \times C_1^y \times C_1^y} \quad (8)$$

By applying laws of indices I have

$$(C_1)^{y+y} + (B_1 \times C_1 \times C_1)^y = (C_1)^{z+y+y}$$

$$C_1^{2y} + (B_1 \times C_1 \times C_1)^y = (C_1)^{2y+z} \quad (9)$$

C_1 is a common prime factor of above equation .

After adjusting the exponents of equation 9 Beal conjecture can be formed .

Comment – Beal conjecture is true for condition 2

6.2.1 numerical example

Derivation of Beal conjecture from equation $1+16=17$

Solution –

$$1+16=17$$

$$1+2^4=17^1$$

Multiplying the equation 2 times by 17^4

$$1 \times 17^4 \times 17^4 + 2^4 \times 17^4 \times 17^4 = 17^1 \times 17^4 \times 17^4$$

By applying the law of indices I can get

$$17^{4+4} + (2 \times 17 \times 17)^4 = 17^{1+4+4}$$

$$17^8 + (578)^4 = 17^9$$

Adjusting the powers of equation we can get Beal conjecture

$$17^8 + (578)^4 = (4913)^3$$

Comment – 17 is the common prime factor in the above equation.

Solution 2 –

$$1+256=257$$

$$1+4^4=257$$

Multiplying through by 257^4

$$1 \times 257^4 \times 257^4 + 4^4 \times 257^4 \times 257^4 = 257^1 \times 257^4 \times 257^4$$

By applying the rules of indices

$$257^{4+4} + (4 \times 257 \times 257)^4 = (257)^{1+4+4}$$

$$257^8 + (264196)^4 = (257)^9$$

$$\text{Or } (257)^8 + (264196)^4 = (16974593)^3$$

Comment – 257 is the common prime factor in the above equation .

Other examples-

$$81 + 256 = 337$$

$$3^4 + 4^4 = 337$$

Multiply the equation two times by 337^4

$$3^4 \times 337^4 \times 337^4 + 4^4 \times 337^4 \times 337^4 = 337^1 \times 337^4 \times 337^4$$

By applying the law of indices I can get

$$(3 \times 337 \times 337)^4 + 2^8 \times 337^8 = 337^{1+4+4}$$

$$(340707)^4 + (674)^8 = (337)^9$$

Comment – 337 is common prime factor in above equation.

Example 2-

$$729+616=1409$$

$$9^3+6^3=1409$$

Multiplying through 1409^3 two times

$$9^3 \times 1409^3 \times 1409^3 + 6^3 \times 1409^3 \times 1409^3 = 1409^1 \times 1409^3 \times 1409^3$$

Applying the rules of indices we can get

$$3^6 \times 1409^6 + (6 \times 1409 \times 1409)^3 = (1409)^{1+3+3}$$

$$(4227)^6 + (11911686)^3 = (1409)^7$$

Comment – 1409 is a common prime factor in the above equation.

6.3 Condition 3

$$E_a + E_b = E_c$$

Let 'E_a' Represent A

Let 'E_b' Represent B

Let 'E_c' Represent C

$$A + B = C \quad (10)$$

Let $A \neq 1$, Let $B \neq 1$ and Let $C \neq 1$

$$A = B \text{ and } C = 2A = 2B$$

Where $x \geq 3$, $y \geq 3$ and $z \geq 4$

Where equation 10 is an ordinary addition operation and variables are in an exponential form

$$A_1^x + B_1^y = C_1^z \quad (11)$$

According to author observation C_1^x or C_1^y or A_1^x or B_1^y multiplies through the equation two times.

$$A_1^x \times A_1^x \times A_1^x + B_1^y \times B_1^y \times B_1^y = C_1^z \times B_1^y \times B_1^y \quad (12)$$

Applying the rule of indices

$$(A_1)^{x+x+x} + (B_1)^{y+y+y} = (C_1)^{z+y+y}$$

$$(A_1)^{3x} + (B_1)^{3y} = (C_1)^{z+2y} \quad (13)$$

$A_1 = B_1 = C_1$ is the common prime factor of above equation.

Comment- $A_1 = B_1 = C_1$ are common prime factor in above equation and Beal conjecture is true for condition 3 .

6.3.1 Numerical example

Derivation of Beal conjecture from equation

$$8+8=16$$

Solution –

$$8+8=16$$

$$2^3+2^3=2^4$$

Multiplying through 2^3 two times.

$$2^3 \times 2^3 \times 2^3 + 2^3 \times 2^3 \times 2^3 = 2^4 \times 2^3 \times 2^3$$

Applying the rule of indices I can get

$$2^{3+3+3} + 2^{3+3+3} = 2^{4+3+3}$$

$$2^9 + 2^9 = 2^{10}$$

Adjusting the exponents of the equation I can get a suitable Beal equation with different powers.

$$8^3 + 2^9 = 4^5$$

Comment- 2 is common prime factor of above equation .

Example 2-

$$32+32=64$$

$$2^5+2^5=2^6$$

Multiplying two times by 2^5

$$2^5 \times 2^5 \times 2^5 + 2^5 \times 2^5 \times 2^5 = 2^5 \times 2^5 \times 2^6$$

Now applying the rules of indices

$$2^{5+5+5} + 2^{5+5+5} = 2^{5+5+6}$$

$$2^{15} + 2^{15} = 2^{16}$$

Or

$$8^5 + 2^{15} = 4^8$$

Comment- 2 is common prime factor in the above equation and it also satisfies truly the Beal conjecture.

7. conclusion-

Author very clearly proved the Beal conjecture. According to real definition of theorem represented a common prime factor with distinct exponents. So Beal conjecture is quite true for all three conditions.

References

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